

Synthesis and spectroscopic characterization of heterobimetallic dioxouranium(VI), trioxomolybdenum(VI), zinc(II), copper(II), nickel(II), cobalt(II) and manganese(II) complexes derived from bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde)malonoyldihydrazone

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Manuscript received 09 November 2011, revised 18 June 2012, accepted 11 July 2012

Abstract : Heterobimetallic complexes $[M_2Zn_2(H_2L)_2(OAc)_4(H_2O)_2]$ ($M = UO_2^{VI}, Cu^{II}, Co^{II}$), $[(MoO_3)_2Zn_2(H_2L)_2(H_2O)_2]$, $[M'_2Zn_2(L)_2(H_2O)_n] \cdot xH_2O$ ($M' = Ni^{II}, n = 4, x = 4$ and $Mn^{II}, n = 6, x = 2$) and homometallic complex $[Zn_4(L)_2(H_2O)_4] \cdot 2H_2O$ have been synthesized from reaction of monometallic zinc complex $[Zn(H_2L)(H_2O)]$ of bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde)malonoyldihydrazone with appropriate metal salts in different experimental conditions in ethanol/methanol media. The composition of the complexes has been established based on data obtained from elemental analyses, thermoanalytical analyses, mass spectrometric studies and molecular weight determination. The structural assessment of the complexes has been done on the basis of molecular weight, electrical conductance, magnetic moment data and variety of spectral studies.

Keywords : Heterometallic complexes, bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde)malonoyldihydrazone, molecular weight, molar conductance, magnetic moment, spectral studies.

Introduction

Almost all the first row transition metal ions occur in the biological systems except scandium and titanium. The metal ions in the enzymes occur either alone or in combination with another metal of their own kind or different kind giving rise to monometallic, homobimetallic and heterobimetallic enzymes¹⁻⁵.

The chemistry of the polyfunctional metal complexes has become a fascinating area of research in contemporary coordination chemistry in view of the above importance of multimetallic metal sites in several enzymes and development of novel functional materials showing molecular ferromagnetism and specific catalytic properties. Dihydrazone derived from condensation of acyl-, aroyl- and pyridoyl-dihydrazone with *o*-hydroxy aromatic aldehydes and ketones are polyfunctional ligands possessing four oxygen and four nitrogen donor atoms⁶. As the growth of the interest in the use of polyfunctional ligands containing electron-withdrawing bulky fragments in their

molecular skeleton becomes more significant⁷⁻⁹, we are interested in the synthesis and characterization of the heterobimetallic metal complexes derived from polyfunctional ligands containing electron withdrawing bulky naphthyl fragments in their molecular skeleton. A survey of literature reveals that although metal complexes of monoacylhydrazones, aroylhydrazones and pyridoylhydrazones have been studied in some greater details¹⁰⁻¹⁵, those of acyl-, aroyl- and pyridoyl-dihydrazone have received attention in recent years only¹⁶⁻²⁰. Further, the reported existence of heterobimetallic complexes of dihydrazones is virtually absent²¹.

In view of the above importance of the bi- or polynuclear and heteropolymetallic complexes, virtual absence of work on heterobimetallic complexes of dihydrazones, the present paper aims at synthesis and characterization of some heterobimetallic complexes with polyfunctional-dihydrazone bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde)malonoyldihydrazone (H_4L) (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde)malonoyldihydrazone (H_4L).

Experimental

The metal salts $UO_2(OAc)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, $(NH_4)_6Mo_7O_{24} \cdot 4H_2O$, $ZnCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, $Zn(OAc)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, $Cu(OAc)_2 \cdot H_2O$, $Ni(OAc)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$, $Co(OAc)_2 \cdot H_2O$ and $Mn(OAc)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$, diethylmalonate, hydrazine hydrate and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde were E. Merck reagents. The organic solvents were purified by standard literature procedures. DMSO was spectroscopic grade.

The ligand bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde)malonoyldihydrazone (H_4L) and the precursor zinc(II) complex $[Zn(H_2L)(H_2O)]$ were prepared as described earlier²². Metals in the complexes were determined by standard literature method²³. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were determined microanalytically using CHN-OS Analyzer: Perkin-Elmer 2400 Series II model. Water molecules in the complexes were determined from the percentage weight losses obtained by heating the samples in an electronic hot air oven. The detailed thermal analyses of the complexes in the temperature range 60–250 °C were carried out, the samples were heated manually at each of the temperatures 60, 65, 70, 75,250 °C for half an hour. The weight loss was determined by subtracting the weight of the complex obtained after heating from weight of the complex before heating, and the losses were calculated.

The thermogravimetric studies were carried out on Mettler Toledo Star system. The molecular weights of

the complexes were determined in DMSO solution by freezing point depression method. The APCI mass spectra of the complexes were recorded on a Water ZQ4000 Micromaas spectrometer. The molar conductances of the complexes at 10^{-3} M dilution in DMSO solution were measured on a Direct Reading Conductivity meter-303 with a dip-type conductivity cell at room temperature. Room temperature magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out on a Vibrating Sample Magnetometer. Experimental magnetic susceptibility values have been corrected for diamagnetism by the procedures given by Figgis and Lewis²⁴. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Paragon-500 Model Infrared spectrophotometer in the range 4000–350 cm^{-1} in KBr discs. The 1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on EM-390, 90 MHz and 25.16 MHz spectrometer in $DMSO-d_6$, respectively, using TMS as an internal standard. The electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded on a Milton Roy Spectronic-21 spectrophotometer. The EPR spectra of the complexes in powdered form as well as in CH_3CN -DMSO solution at room temperature and liquid nitrogen temperature were recorded at X-band frequency on a Varian E-112 X/Q-band spectrometer using DPPH ($g = 2.0036$) as an internal field marker.

Preparation of heterobimetallic complexes
 $[M_2Zn_2(H_2L)_2(OAc)_4(H_2O)_2]$ ($M = UO_2^{VI}$ (1), Cu^{II} (3), Co^{II} (5)); $[(MoO_3)_2Zn_2(H_2L)_2(H_2O)_2]$ (2), $[M'_2Zn_2(L)_2(H_2O)_n] \cdot xH_2O$ ($M' = Ni^{II}$ (4), $n = 4$, $x = 4$; Mn^{II} (6), $n = 6$, $x = 2$) and $[Zn_4(L)_2(H_2O)_4] \cdot 2H_2O$ (7):

In order to prepare heterometallic complex (1), $[Zn(H_2L)(H_2O)]$ (0.52 g, 1.00 mmol) was suspended in ethanol (30 mL) and stirred gently for 15 min at 70 °C. The above suspension was added drop by drop at 70 °C over a period of 15 min into a solution of $UO_2(OAc)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ (0.47 g, 1.10 mmol) in ethanol (30 mL) containing a drop of acetic acid accompanied by gentle stirring. The resulting solution was refluxed for 3 h which precipitated a light brown compound. The compound thus precipitated was filtered, washed with ethanol, ether and dried over anhydrous $CaCl_2$. Yield : 0.78 g.

The complexes (3) to (6) were also prepared by essentially following the above procedure using metal acetates

[Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Mn^{II}] in place of UO₂(OAc)₂.2H₂O without adding acetic acid from outside. In case of heterometallic Cu^{II}-Zn^{II} complex (3), methanol was used as the reaction medium. For preparing homometallic complex (7), Zn(OAc)₂.4H₂O was used. The heterometallic complex (2) was also synthesized by essentially following the above procedure using MoO₂(acac)₂ in place of metal acetates.

Results and discussion

The monometallic zinc(II) complex [Zn(H₂L)(H₂O)] was allowed to react with metal acetates (M = UO₂^{VI}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Mn^{II} and Zn^{II} in 1 : 1.1 molar ratio in ethanol, the heterometallic complexes [(UO₂)₂Zn₂(H₂L)₂(OAc)₄(H₂O)₂] (1), [M₂Zn₂(H₂L)₂(OAc)₄(H₂O)₂] (M = Cu^{II} (3), Co^{II} (5)) and [M₂'Zn₂(L)₂(H₂O)_n].xH₂O (M' = Ni^{II} (4), n = 4, x = 4; Mn^{II} (6), n = 6, x = 2) and the homometallic complex [Zn₄(L)₂(H₂O)₄].2H₂O (7) were obtained. On the other hand, the reaction of [Zn(H₂L)(H₂O)] with MoO₂(acac)₂ in 1 : 1.1 molar ratio in ethanol resulted in the formation of heterometallic complex [(MoO₃)₂Zn₂(H₂L)₂(H₂O)₂] (2).

The analytical and physical data of the complexes have been set out in Table 1. The complexes are air stable and decompose between 275–295 °C except the complex (1) which decomposes above 300 °C. They are yellow, orange, brown and dark brown in colour, respectively. The freshly prepared complexes are sparingly soluble in water and common organic solvents. However, all of the complexes are easily soluble in highly coordinating solvents like DMSO and DMF. The detailed decomposition studies²⁵ of the complexes were carried out manually in the temperature range 60–250 °C by heating the samples in an electronic oven for half an hour at each of the temperature 60, 65, 70, 75, 250 °C, respectively. The weight loss was determined by subtracting the weight of the complex obtained after heating from the weight of the complex before heating and thus the weight losses and percentage weight losses were calculated. The complex (4) showed weight loss corresponding to four water molecules in the temperature range 80–130 °C while the complexes (6) and (7) showed weight losses corresponding to two water molecules in the temperature range 80–

130 °C indicated that they are present in the lattice of the complexes. On the other hand, the complexes (1) to (3) and (5) showed weight loss corresponding to two water molecules in the temperature range 160–210 °C while, in the same temperature range, the complex (4) and (7) showed loss of weight corresponding to four water molecules, and the complex (6) showed weight loss corresponding to six water molecules, respectively. The fact that these water molecules are lost in the temperature range 160–210 °C suggests that they are present in the first coordination sphere around the metal centre. The molar conductance for the complexes lies in 1.6–2.6 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ region in DMSO solution at 10⁻³ M dilution indicating their non-electrolytic nature²⁶.

Thermogravimetric studies :

The heterometallic Ni^{II}-Zn^{II} complex (4) has been characterized by thermogravimetric studies as shown in Fig. 2. The decomposition of the complex occurs in the four prominent steps, i.e. 80–240, 285–350, 395–490 and above 500 °C. The complex loses mass steadily in one step between 80 and 240 °C, the average mass loss being 1.6% at 20 °C temperature interval, which corresponds to eight water molecules. This indicates that lattice and coordinated water molecules are lost simultaneously in a single continuous step. The simultaneous loss of lattice and coordinated water molecules may, most probably, be due to the hydrogen bond network that permeates the lattice. The hydrogen bond may be between the lattice-held water molecules and coordinated water molecules. On the basis of mass loss at 180 and 110 °C, it is suggested that four water molecules are coordinated to the metal centres and four water molecules are held in the lattice by hydrogen bonding with the coordinated water molecules. After the initial loss of water molecules, the mass of the complex remains almost constant over 240–285 °C. The most significant decomposition of the complex occurs in the temperature range 285–490 °C in which loss of the ligand occurs. Although, the decomposition of the complex in temperature range 285–490 °C is a two step process, yet once started, it occurs simultaneously. The first decomposition step occurs between 285–350 °C while the second decomposition step occurs between 395–

Table 1. Complexes (empirical formulae), molecular formulae, colour, decomposition point, % yield, molecular weight, magnetic moment and molar conductance data for heterobimetallic complexes

Sl. no.	Complex : Molecular formula (Emp. formula) Colour	Mol. wt. (Theo.)	D. p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				Mag. mom. (B.M.)	Molar cond. (Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹)	
					Zn	M	C	H			N
1.	[(UO ₂) ₂ Zn ₂ (H ₂ L) ₂ (OAc) ₄ (H ₂ O) ₂] ((UO ₂ Zn(H ₂ L)(OAc) ₂ (H ₂ O)) ₂) C ₅₈ H ₅₂ N ₈ O ₂₂ Zn ₂ U ₂ Light brown	1900 ± 60 (1818.76)	> 300	85	7.25 (7.19)	26.55 (26.17)	38.68 (38.27)	2.82 (2.86)	6.36 (6.16)	Dia	2.5
2.	[(MoO ₃) ₂ Zn ₂ (H ₂ L) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂] ((MoO ₃ Zn(H ₂ L)(H ₂ O)) ₂) C ₅₀ H ₄₀ N ₈ O ₁₆ Zn ₂ Mo ₂ Orange	1400 ± 40 (1330.76)	280	70	10.10 (9.83)	14.91 (14.43)	45.49 (45.09)	3.05 (3.01)	8.80 (8.42)	Dia	1.6
3.	[Cu ₂ Zn ₂ (H ₂ L) ₂ (OAc) ₄ (H ₂ O) ₂] ((CuZn(H ₂ L)(OAc) ₂ (H ₂ O)) ₂) C ₅₈ H ₅₂ N ₈ O ₁₈ Zn ₂ Cu ₂ Greenish yellow	1500 ± 45 (1405.84)	275	86	9.31 (9.04)	9.58 (9.30)	49.95 (49.51)	3.65 (3.70)	8.10 (7.97)	1.32	1.9
4.	[NiZn ₂ (L) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄].4H ₂ O ((NiZn(L)(H ₂ O) ₂).2H ₂ O) C ₅₀ H ₄₈ N ₈ O ₁₆ Zn ₂ Ni ₂ Yellow	1450 ± 42 (1264.14)	285	75	10.65 (10.34)	9.50 (9.29)	47.88 (47.46)	3.75 (3.80)	9.10 (8.86)	2.80	2.6
5.	[Co ₂ Zn ₂ (H ₂ L) ₂ (OAc) ₄ (H ₂ O) ₂] ((CoZn(H ₂ L)(OAc) ₂ (H ₂ O)) ₂) C ₅₈ H ₅₂ N ₈ O ₁₈ Zn ₂ Co ₂ Dark brown	1550 ± 50 (1396.62)	290	70	9.71 (9.37)	8.72 (8.44)	50.10 (49.85)	3.70 (3.73)	8.35 (8.02)	3.12	1.9
6.	[Mn ₂ Zn ₂ (L) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆].2H ₂ O ((MnZn(L)(H ₂ O) ₃).H ₂ O) C ₅₀ H ₄₈ N ₈ O ₁₆ Zn ₂ Mn ₂ Brown	1500 ± 45 (1256.16)	275	65	10.15 (10.41)	8.55 (8.74)	47.60 (47.75)	3.80 (3.82)	9.10 (8.91)	5.80	1.8
7.	[Zn ₄ (L) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄].2H ₂ O ((Zn ₂ (L) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂).H ₂ O) C ₅₀ H ₄₄ N ₈ O ₁₄ Zn ₄ Yellow	1430 ± 40 (1241.52)	290	75	21.56 (21.07)	-	47.89 (48.33)	3.50 (3.54)	8.82 (9.02)	Dia	1.5

Fig. 2. TG/DTG curve of the complex $[\text{Ni}_2\text{Zn}_2(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4].4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (4).

490 °C. In both decomposition steps, the mass loss, on an average is about 22% which corresponds to half of naphthyl fraction of the coordinated dihydrazone in each step. Above 490 °C, the complex loses mass steadily until a constant weight is attained above 700 °C, which corresponds to combined weight of zinc oxide and nickel oxide.

Molecular weight :

The fact that the structures are discrete molecules has been proven by determining the molecular weights of all the complexes (Table 1) in DMSO. The experimental values of the molecular weights for the complexes (1) to (3) and (5) were found to be close to the theoretical values calculated for dimeric formulation. This confirms that these complexes have dimeric structures. However, for the complexes (4), (6) and (7), the experimental values are much higher than the values calculated for the dimeric formulation. Such a high experimental value of molecular weight strongly suggests that the structures of the complexes are altered in the strongly coordinating solvents as compared to that in the solid state. Most probably, the coordinated water molecules are substituted by DMSO molecules, which accounts for the higher molecular weight

of the complexes.

Mass spectra :

The complexes $[\text{Cu}_2\text{Zn}_2(\text{H}_2\text{L})_2(\text{OAc})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (3) and $[\text{Ni}_2\text{Zn}_2(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4].4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (4) were studied by mass spectrometry to make an assessment of the molecular complexity of the complexes. The complex $[\text{Cu}_2\text{Zn}_2(\text{H}_2\text{L})_2(\text{OAc})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (3) shows a strong peak at m/z value of 1392.2. This peak is assigned to the molecular ion $[\text{Cu}_2\text{Zn}_2(\text{H}_2\text{L})_2(\text{OAc})_3(\text{DMSO})]^+$ (1390.84) which is obtained by the loss of coordinated water molecules from the complex followed by coordination of one solvent molecule DMSO²⁷. On the other hand, the complex $[\text{Ni}_2\text{Zn}_2(\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4].4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (4) shows a peak at m/z value of 1278.3 in its mass spectra. This peak may be assigned to arise from the molecular ion $[\text{Ni}_2\text{Zn}_2(\text{H}_2\text{L})_2(\text{DMSO})_2]^+$ (1278.46). This ionic species results, most probably, from loss of coordinated water from the dimeric complex followed by coordination of two DMSO molecules in DMSO solution. Such mass spectral features of the complexes suggest that they are dimeric in nature²⁷.

Proton nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy :

Four and two proton signals observed in the δ 11.11–12.96 ppm and δ 8.40–9.48 ppm regions downfield of

TMS have been assigned to $\delta\text{OH} + \delta\text{NH}$ and $\delta\text{CH}=\text{N}$ protons^{12,16-18}, respectively (Table 2). The multiplet due to aromatic protons appears in the δ 7.03–8.30 ppm region. The signal at δ 3.60 ppm is attributed to arise due

of these signals is upfield shifted by 0.15 and 0.37 ppm as compared to that in the free dihydrazone and by 0.02 and 0.20 as compared to that in the precursor monometallic zinc(II) complexes. This rules out the possibility of

Table 2. ¹H NMR spectral data (in δ) for dihydrazone, precursor monometallic complex and some heterobimetallic complexes

Sl. no.	Complex	δCH_2	$\delta(\text{naphthyl})$	$\delta(-\text{CH}=\text{N})$ (<i>J</i> , Hz)	$\delta\text{OH} + \delta\text{NH}$ (<i>J</i> , Hz)
1.	H ₄ L	3.90	7.03–8.30 (m)	9.30 (d, 32.9)	12.65 (d, 63.0)
		3.60		8.60 (d, 32.9)	11.50 (d, 63.0)
2.	[Zn(H ₂ L)(H ₂ O)]	3.85	7.18–8.57 (m)	9.23 (d, 35.1)	12.48 (d, 56.7)
		3.50		8.78 (d, 35.1)	11.35 (d, 56.7)
3.	[(UO ₂) ₂ Zn ₂ (H ₂ L) ₂ (OAc) ₄ (H ₂ O) ₂]	-	7.17–8.57 (m)	9.82 (d, 53.6)	12.50 (d, 66.2)
		-		8.89 (d, 53.6)	11.30 (d, 66.2)
4.	[(MoO ₃) ₂ Zn ₂ (H ₂ L) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	3.80	7.10–8.50 (m)	9.62 (d, 39.2)	12.28 (d, 59.0)
		3.47		8.85 (d, 39.2)	11.16 (d, 59.0)
5.	[Zn ₄ (L) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄].2H ₂ O	3.82	7.13–8.20 (m)	9.30 (d, 27.9)	-
		3.58		8.60 (d, 27.9)	-

to methylene protons ($-\text{CH}_2-$), while that at δ 3.90 ppm is attributed to methyne proton ($=\text{CH}-$). The appearance of methylene protons in the form of two signals indicates that the dihydrazone exists in keto-enol equilibrium in solution involving methylene protons as shown below.

The heterobimetallic complexes (1) and (2) show two doublets in the regions δ 11.16–12.50 ppm and 8.85–9.82 ppm, respectively, similar to that in the free dihydrazone and the monometallic precursor zinc(II) complex¹¹. The signals in the region δ 11.16–12.50 ppm region are slightly modified and weak broad in the complexes as compared to that in the free dihydrazone in which they are relatively intense. This suggests that they arise due to secondary $-\text{NH}$ protons^{16,18}, only indicating coordination of the naphtholic $-\text{OH}$ groups to the metal centres via deprotonation. Further, the average positions

of these signals is upfield shifted by 0.15 and 0.37 ppm as compared to that in the free dihydrazone and by 0.02 and 0.20 as compared to that in the precursor monometallic zinc(II) complexes. This rules out the possibility of involvement of secondary $-\text{NH}$ group in bonding. The essential features associated with the ¹H NMR spectra of the complexes in the δ 11.16–12.50 ppm region indicate that the conformation of the dihydrazone remains unaltered on complexation. The azomethine proton signals are also downfield shifted by 0.41 and 0.29 ppm in the complexes (1) and (2) as compared to that in the free dihydrazone and by 0.35 and 0.23 ppm as compared to that in the precursor complex, indicating bonding of azomethine nitrogen atoms to the metal centres. It is interesting to note that these signals are further downfield shifted. This suggests that the bonding between azomethine nitrogen atoms and metal centres is stronger in heterobimetallic complexes as compared to that in the precursor complex^{22,28}. On the other hand, in the complex (7), the signal in the region δ 11.00–13.00 ppm is absent indicating that secondary $-\text{NH}$ and naphtholic $-\text{OH}$ protons disappear in the homobimetallic complex. This suggests enolization of the dihydrazone and its coordination through enolate and naphtholate oxygen atoms via deprotonation²⁹. The $\delta\text{CH}=\text{N}$ signals appear in the form of four resonances (two doublets) in all of the three complexes (1), (2) and (7). Another point of interest is the methylene proton signal which appears in the form of two resonances. This suggests that the complexes exist in keto-enol equilibrium in DMSO solution.

It is to be noted that the methylene protons appear in the region δ 3.47–3.60 ppm while the methine protons appear in the region δ 3.80–4.23 ppm in the free ligand as well as the metal complexes. The position of methine protons is very close to the value in the region δ 3.92–4.35 ppm observed in several alkene type of organic molecules³⁰.

¹³C NMR spectroscopy :

The dihydrazone and the heterobimetallic complex [MoO₃Zn(CH₂LH₂)(H₂O)] (2) have been characterized by ¹³C NMR spectroscopy. The chemical shift δ (ppm from SiMe₄) and the chemical shift changes $\Delta\delta$ (ppm) accompanying the coordination of the ligand in complex are reported in Table 3.

Table 3. ¹³C NMR spectral data for dihydrazone and complex [(MoO₃)₂Zn₂(H₂L)₂(H₂O)₂] (2)

H ₄ L Carbon atoms	[(MoO ₃) ₂ Zn ₂ (H ₂ L) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]		
	δ^x	δ^x	$\Delta\delta^y$
C(2a), C(2b)	168.3, 167.8	168.3, 167.8	0
C(2a'), C(2b')	162.6, 162.2	162.5, 162.2	+0.05
C(13a), C(13b)	157.8, 156.7	188.5, 187.5	-30.75
C(3a), C(3b)	146.0, 145.6	157.3, 157.0, 156.8	-11.23
C(10a), C(10b)	142.9, 142.5	146.4, 145.6	-3.3
C(5a), C(5b)	132.8, 132.4	142.0, 142.6	-10.2
C(9a), C(9b)	131.4, 131.1	132.0, 131.6, 131.3	-0.38
C(7a), C(7b)	128.9, 128.6	128.8, 128.4	+0.15
C(8a), C(8b)	127.8, 127.6	127.8, 128.0	0.10
C(6a), C(6b)	123.5, 123.3	124.7, 125.3	-1.60
C(4a), C(4b)	121.0, 120.8	120.25	+0.65
C(12a), C(12b)	118.1, 118.0	118.0, 117.9	+0.15
C(11a), C(11b)	108.4, 108.3	111.2, 108.60, 108.2	-0.98
C(1b)	110.1	110.10	0
C(1a)	41.5	41.4	+0.10

The numbering scheme for the carbon atoms for both ligand and complex is the same. The carbon atoms in the axial and equatorial positions have been designated by letters 'a' and 'b' respectively.

In the complex, many signals are split resulting into more number of signals as a result of coordination than those in the free ligand. The effect of metal ions on carbon resonances of naphthyl ring, thus, downfield shifts the signals C(6), C(8), C(9) and C(11) atleast 1.60–10.00 ppm, respectively. On the other hand, the signals due to

C(4), C(7) and C(12) shift upfield by δ 0.15–0.65 ppm, respectively. The average position of the resonance due to carbonyl carbon atoms are also shifted upfield by +0.05 ppm. The shift to higher field of the signal due to C(2) rules out the possibility of coordination of >C=O group to the metal ions. The resonance due to the C(13) and C(3) are much downfield shifted since they are closer to the coordinated oxygen and nitrogen atoms. As a consequence, the signals for C(13) and C(3) which in the free ligand, were at 157.8, 156.7 ppm and 146.0, 145.6 ppm, respectively, could be either in the region δ 156.8–157.3 ppm or in the region 187.5–188.5 ppm and in the region 145.6–146.4 ppm or in the region 156.8–157.3 ppm, respectively, in the complexes. The latter assignments are much more likely, since they give a deshielding of δ 30.75 and 11.23 ppm, respectively, whereas the former assignments give insignificant shielding of 0.22 ppm or deshielding of 0.02 ppm, respectively. The signals at δ 145.6, 146.4 ppm in the complex could be assigned to C(10) while those at δ 142.6, 1430.0 ppm could be assigned to C(5) carbon atoms. These carbon atoms absorb at δ 142.5, 142.9 and δ 132.4, 132.8 ppm, respectively, in free dihydrazone giving chemical shift changes of 3.30 ppm and 10.2 ppm, respectively. The signals at δ 120.25 ppm are assigned to C(4a) and C(4b) carbon atoms which in free ligand appeared at δ 120.8, 121.0 ppm, giving upfield shift of about +0.65 ppm. Such a feature associated with C(4) resonances may be attributed to combined effect of drainage of electron density from azomethine nitrogen atoms in opposite direction. In view of the above spectral features and discussion of the ¹³C NMR spectra of both the ligand and complex, it is reasonable to suggest that the coordinated ligand in the metal complexes has the same conformation as that in the free state and that the dihydrazone is coordinated to the metal centre in the *anti-cis* configuration.

It is remarkable to note that the complex shows signals at δ 110.10 ppm and 41.4 ppm corresponding to methylene group. The appearance of signals at δ 110.10 and 41.4 ppm in the complex (2) corresponding to methylene group indicates that the coordinated ligand exists in enol and keto forms in the solution state and that the signals correspond to methyne and methylene protons, respectively. The appearance of signals may be attributed

to occurrence of a dynamic process in the solution in which the complex undergoes dissociation and that the dissociated complex remains in equilibrium with the undissociated complex. The dissociated complex readily reassembles giving rise to undissociated complex.

Infrared spectra :

The complexes (1) and (2) shows a strong band in the region 3300–3500 cm^{-1} while another strong band at 3190 and 3180 cm^{-1} , respectively. The strong band in the region 3300–3500 cm^{-1} is assigned to νOH vibration of coordinated water while that around 3190 cm^{-1} to νNH vibration of secondary NH group. In the remaining complexes, a strong broad band is observed in the region 3000–3560 cm^{-1} . This band is assigned to have composite character due to νNH vibration of secondary -NH group and νOH vibration of coordinated water molecules in the complexes (3) and (5) while to asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibration of coordinated as well as lattice held water molecules in the complexes (4), (6) and (7).

The complexes (1) to (3) and (5) show either a single strong band (complex (1)) or a couple of bands in the region 1665–1695 cm^{-1} due to amide I. On an average, these bands are shifted to higher frequency in the complexes by 2–16 cm^{-1} as compared to that in the precursor complex. This indicates that $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ groups do not take part in coordination, similar to that in the precursor monometallic complex²².

On the other band, in the complexes (4), (6) and (7), the situation is quite different. The strong band appearing at 1672 cm^{-1} in the precursor complex disappears in these complexes. This suggests enolization of the dihydrazone in these complexes. All of the complexes show a couple of very strong bands in the region 1597–1618 cm^{-1} . This band is assigned to stretching vibration of $>\text{C}=\text{N}$ group. This band remains either almost unshifted in position or shifts to higher frequency by 1 to 2 cm^{-1} as compared to those in the precursor complex. Such a feature associated with the $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ band in these complexes indicates that azomethine nitrogen-metal bond in the heterobimetallic complexes is either of the same strength as that in the precursor monometallic complex or slightly weakened^{17,18}.

The band appearing at 1278 and 1280 cm^{-1} in the free

ligand and precursor zinc complex, respectively due to $\beta(\text{C}-\text{O})$ vibrations shifts to higher frequency by 5–20 cm^{-1} as compared to that in the precursor complex indicating bonding between naphtholate oxygen atom and metal centre.

All of the heterobimetallic complexes show a new medium to weak intensity band in the region 800–860 cm^{-1} . This band is characteristic of tetraatomic species

resulted from involvement of naphtholate oxygen atom in bridge formation³¹. The complexes (1), (3) and (5) show new non-ligand bands in the regions 1552–1570 and 1410–1440 cm^{-1} , which are assigned to $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO})$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO})$ vibrations of bridging acetato group³². The complex (1) shows a strong band at 906 cm^{-1} and the heterobimetallic molybdenum(VI) complex (2) shows three new bands at 950, 898 and 874 cm^{-1} assigned to $\nu(\text{UO}_2^{2+})$ and $\nu(\text{MoO}_3)$ stretching vibrations³³. Another new strong band at 749 cm^{-1} is assigned to $\nu(\text{Mo}-\text{O}-\text{Mo})$ vibration³⁴.

It is evident from the above discussion that an oxo-group bonded to molybdenum is generated in complex (2). The mechanism for generation of oxo-group is shown in Scheme 1. In complex (3), MoO_3 group is generated when $\text{MoO}_2(\text{acac})_2$ is allowed to react with the precursor complex $[\text{Zn}(\text{H}_2\text{L})\text{H}_2\text{O}]$.

Magnetic moment and electron paramagnetic resonance spectra :

The complexes (1), (3) and (7) are diamagnetic consistent with f^0 , d^0 and d^{10} configuration of U^{VI} , Mo^{VI} and Zn^{II} , respectively. The heterobimetallic $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}-\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$ and $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}-\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$ complexes (3) and (5) have effective magnetic moment values equal to 1.32 and 2.12 B.M. while the $\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}-\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$ and $\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}-\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$ complexes (4) and (6) have μ_{B} value equal to 2.80 and 5.80 B.M., respectively. The observed effective magnetic moment values for the complexes (3) and (5) are lower than the spin-only value of 1.73 and 3.89 B.M., per Cu^{II} and Co^{II} atom while for the complexes (4) and (6), the values are very close to the spin-only value for presence of two and five unpaired electrons per Ni^{II} and Mn^{II} atom, respectively. This indicates that the complexes (3) and (5) undergo exchange interaction leading to lower μ_{B} values while such exchange interaction is absent in the structural unit of the

complexes (4) and (6). The lowering of the magnetic moment may be either due to direct metal-metal interaction via the overlap of suitable metal orbitals due to super-exchange via overlap of the metal d-orbital with the orbital of the bridging oxygen atom apart from the metal-metal interaction due to stacking of one molecule over the other. Such a magnetic moment behaviour of the complexes may be inherent in their structure. The fact that all the complexes have oxo-bridging involving naphtholate oxygen atoms and that the complexes (4) and (6) are normal paramagnetic suggests that the metal atoms are

arranged in such a fashion in the structural unit of the complexes that the oxo-bridging does not lead to exchange of paramagnetic spin-density between the metal centres in the complexes. This may happen only if transition metal atom and border line metal atom are alternatively arranged in the structural unit in the complexes (4) and (6) but adjacent to one another in the complexes (3) and (5). Hence, it is suggested that in the complexes (4) and (6), the transition metal atom (Ni or Mn) and the borderline metal atom (Zn) are alternately arranged while in the complexes (3) and (5), the transition metal atom (Cu or

Scheme 1. Mechanism for generation of oxo group in complex $[(\text{MoO}_3)_2\text{Zn}_2(\text{H}_2\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$.

Co) are adjacent to one another. Further, that the transition metal atoms in the complexes (3) and (5) are tethered to one another by acetate bridge which leads to metal-metal interaction lowering the magnetic moment.

The various magnetic parameters for the complexes (3) to (6) characterized by EPR studies have been sum-

marized in Table 4. The heterobimetallic copper(II) complex (3) shows anisotropic spectrum with weak signal at $g = 2.108$ at RT (Fig. 3). This signal shows splitting into seven components due to copper hyperfine interactions. For a copper-copper dimer, a seven line pattern (1 : 2 : 3 : 4 : 3 : 2 : 1) is expected. The observed intensities are

Table 4. EPR magnetic parameters and electronic spectral bands for heterobimetallic complexes

Sl. no.	Complexes	Temp.	Magnetic parameters		Electronic spectral band; λ_{\max} (ϵ_{\max})	
			g_{av}	A_{av} (G)	CH ₃ CN	DMSO
	H ₄ L	-	-	-	320, 390	-
	[Zn(H ₂ L)(H ₂ O)]	-	-	-	360, 405, 460	365 (15130), 410 (10370), 450 (7350)
1.	[(UO ₂) ₂ Zn ₂ (H ₂ L) ₂ (OAc) ₄ (H ₂ O) ₂]	-	-	-	370, 435, 475, 520	370 (12490), 430 (10230), 470 (10230), 525 (25)
2.	[(MoO ₃) ₂ Zn ₂ (H ₂ L) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	-	-	-	360, 410, 465	360 (13280), 405 (9650), 46 (6490)
3.	[Cu ₂ Zn ₂ (H ₂ L) ₂ (OAc) ₄ (H ₂ O) ₂]	RT (solid)	2.108	38	380, 490, 710	390 (13150), 450 (10370), 500 (8370), 710 (35)
4.	[Ni ₂ Zn ₂ (L) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄].4H ₂ O	LNT (solid)	2.025	34	350, 400, 475	310 (12780), 400 (15270), 480 (11560), 690 (42)
5.	[Co ₂ Zn ₂ (H ₂ L) ₂ (OAc) ₄ (H ₂ O) ₂]	LNT (solid)	2.035	-	340, 400, 445, 560	340 (11560), 400 (13270), 440 (7450), 570 (45)

Fig. 3. Solid state EPR spectrum of the complex [Cu₂Zn₂(H₂L)₂(OAc)₄(H₂O)₂] (3) at RT, Field set : 3200 G; Scan range : 5000 G; Frequency : 9.52 GHz.

not consistent with the predicted ratio although the central line is the most intense. The isotropic nuclear hyperfine coupling constant A_{av} is found to be 38 G. This value is typical of complexes having considerable copper-copper interaction resulting in the dimer formation³⁵. The EPR spectrum of the complex $[\text{NiZn}(\text{L})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**4**) was recorded at RT as well as LNT at 9.1 GHz. The complex is EPR silent at both RT as well as LNT. In the nickel(II) complexes, the zero-field splitting (zfs) ranges from a few to some tens of wave numbers. Consequently, the conventional X-band and Q-band EPR spectroscopy using electromagnetic quanta around 0.3 and 1.5 cm^{-1} find it difficult to excite transitions between the states of the spin-triplet manifold. Further, four-coordinate square-planar/five-coordinate centres present in hydrogenase enzyme and the reduced states of the C-cluster in the bacterial carbon monoxide dehydrogenase enzyme are EPR silent. On the other hand, four-coordinate tetrahedral and six-coordinate octahedral nickel(II) complexes are EPR active. The observed spectral features of the complex suggest that it is EPR silent indicating that nickel(II) is present either as four-coordinate square-planar or five-coordinate square-pyramidal centre in the complex. The possibility of existence of four-coordinate square-planar geometry around nickel(II) centre in the complex is ruled out on the basis of its magnetic moment values which corresponds to the presence of two unpaired electrons. Hence, it is suggested that the stereochemistry around nickel(II) centre in the complex is five-coordinate square-pyramidal³⁶. The heterometallic cobalt(II) complex (**5**) is EPR silent at RT which is consistent with the occurrence of high-spin cobalt(II). However, at LNT, the complex shows a fifteen line spectrum with coupling constant 34 G. This shows that spin cross-over to low-spin form occurs at low temperature³⁷ and that the two cobalt(II) centres are coupled to each other. The EPR spectrum of the manganese complex (**6**) shows an isotropic signal at RT as broad single resonance with $g \cong 2.0$ without manganese hyperfine structure. This indicates its nearly axial symmetry having small distortions from octahedral stereochemistry. Dowsing *et al.*³⁸ observed a similar $g \cong 2.0$ centred resonance for the complex $\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}(\text{picoline})\text{Cl}_2$. They explained these observations as resulting from a polymeric structure giving extensive intermolecular magnetic interaction. The DMSO solution EPR spectrum of this complex at RT as well as at LNT are characteristic of

spin-free manganese(II) ruling out the possibility of M–M interaction. The metal hyperfine splitting constant is 94 G which is typical for manganese(II) oxidation state. Between every pair of the six hyperfine lines of $g \cong 2.0$ resonance, there is a pair of relatively weak forbidden transition. The separation between individual levels of a pair is approximately 30.7 G.

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectral bands for dihydrazone ligand, precursor monometallic complex and the heterobimetallic complexes have been set out in Table 4. The free ligand H_4L shows two bands at 320 nm ($\epsilon_{\text{max}} 9500 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$) and 390 nm ($\epsilon_{\text{max}} 15700 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$) in the region 300–400 nm. The band at 320 nm is assigned to intraligand $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition while the band at 390 nm is assigned to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition. The band at 390 nm is characteristic of naphthalimine part as has been reported in several monoacylhydrazones^{10,11}. All of the complexes are sparingly soluble in CH_3CN while completely in DMSO. Hence, their electronic spectra have been recorded qualitatively in CH_3CN while quantitatively in DMSO.

The electronic spectra of the complexes in CH_3CN show three bands in the region 300–700 nm. The ligand bands at 320 and 390 nm show red shift on complexation by 20–60 and 10–45 nm, respectively. The bands appearing in the region 340–380 nm are attributed to ligand band at 320 nm. On the other hand, the band appearing in the region 400–435 nm may be attributed to ligand band at 390 nm. The red shift of the ligand bands gives good evidence of chelation of dihydrazones to the metal centre. The magnitude of red shift of ligand bands on complexation indicates strong bonding between the ligand and the metal centre. The bands in the region 330–435 nm run in the complexes are strong which is indicative of their discrete molecular nature. All of the complexes show a new band in the region 440–500 nm not observed in the free ligand, which has very high molar extinction coefficient. In view of very high molar extinction coefficient of this band and its similarity to the charge transfer band in the precursor complex, it is assigned to have its origin in the ligand-to-metal charge transfer transition from naphtholate oxygen atom to the metal centre³⁹.

The heterobimetallic $\text{UO}_2^{\text{VI}}\text{-Zn}^{\text{II}}$ complex (**1**) shows a new band at ~ 525 nm not observed in the precursor

complex. This band is attributed to arise due to the tri-atomic uranyl ion (UO_2)²⁺⁴⁰. The heterobimetallic Cu^{II} - Zn^{II} complex (3) shows a new weak broad band in the region 650–750 with maximum absorption at 710 nm. The ${}^2T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^2E_g$ transition occurs at ~ 800 nm in octahedral complexes. This band is considerably blue shifted due to Jahn-Teller distortion in copper(II) complexes. The weak broad features of this band suggest that it is most probably overall envelope of the bands arising from ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transitions in order of increasing energy. The band position together with molar extinction coefficients in these complexes suggests that the copper(II) centre in the complex (3) has tetragonally distorted octahedral stereochemistry. The heterobimetallic Ni^{II} - Zn^{II} complex (4) shows a weak band at 690 nm (ϵ_{max} 42 $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$). This band is assigned to ${}^3B_1 \rightarrow {}^3E$ transition resulting from the presence of nickel atom in the complex⁴¹. From position of this band it is reasonable to suggest that nickel(II) is having five-coordinate square-pyramidal geometry in the heterobimetallic complex. Heterobimetallic Co^{II} - Zn^{II} complex (5) shows a weak band at 560 nm in addition to ligand and charge transfer bands. The position of this band is consistent with distorted octahedral stereochemistry in the complex⁴². The electronic spectrum of the Mn^{II} - Zn^{II} complex (6) shows ligand band and charge transfer bands only. Any d-d band occurring in this complex is masked by strong charge-transfer band.

Conclusion :

This work has served some important preparative, stereochemical and physical properties of the heterobimetallic complexes derived from polynucleating dihydrazone H_4L using its monometallic zinc(II) complex as precursor which bears on our ultimate goal of finding cooperative bimetallic reactivity. The monometallic complex $[\text{Zn}(\text{H}_2\text{L})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ allows for the incorporation of different metal ions under very mild conditions leading to the formation of tetranuclear heterobimetallic complexes in all cases. The monometallic complex does not suffer any transmetalation. This work has provided synthetic routes to prepare site specific heterobimetallic complexes. All of the complexes are dimeric. Nickel atom in the complex (4) and zinc atom in all complexes is proposed to have square-pyramidal stereochemistry. In the complex (1) uranium atom is suggested to have eight coordinate hexagonal bipyramidal stereochemistry while the other

metal centres are proposed to have distorted octahedral stereochemistry in the remaining complexes. The tentative structures for the complexes have been shown in Figs. 4–7.

Fig. 4. Tentative structure for the complex $[(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{Zn}_2(\text{H}_2\text{L})_2(\text{OAc})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (1).

Fig. 5. Tentative structure for the complex $[(\text{MoO}_3)_2\text{Zn}_2(\text{H}_2\text{L})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (2).

Fig. 6. Tentative structure for the complexes $[\text{M}_2\text{Zn}_2(\text{H}_2\text{L})_2(\text{OAc})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ [$\text{M} = \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$ (3), Co^{II} (5)].

Fig. 7. Tentative structure for the complexes $[M_2Zn_2(L)_2(H_2O)_nX] \cdot xH_2O$ [$M = Ni^{II}$ (4), $n = 4$; $X = O$, $x = 4$; Mn^{II} (6), $X = H_2O$, $n = 4$; $X = 2$, $x = 2$; Zn^{II} (7), $X = O$, $n = 4$, $X = O$, $x = 2$].

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to the Head, SAIF, North-Eastern Hill University, Shillong, Meghalaya, India for elemental analyses, mass spectral data and to the Head, SAIF, IIT Mumbai, India for EPR spectroscopic studies. The authors are thankful to the Head, SAIF, Nagpur University, Nagpur for thermogravimetric studies.

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